

GENERAL CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL VALUES OF THE OLD CLASSICAL LATIN LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698631>

Annotation. Roman literature is a rich cultural heritage for the peoples of the world. One of them is winged words, literary quotations, figurative expressions and proverbs. We know and are well aware that the use of appropriate proverbs in our speech can give effect and eloquence to our speech. Latin is also a medical language. All terms related to this area are learned in this language. This language is widely taught in medical schools. The purpose of this course is to train future medical professionals in skills such as independent reading in Latin and understanding of medical texts with the help of a dictionary, assimilation of information from scientific literature on the ground and writing by specialty, diagnosis and writing grammatically correct prescriptions.

Key words: statehood, the role of the Latin language, the place of the Latin language in the world community, winged words, philosophical meaning, the language of diplomacy, the Renaissance.

It is known that the Latin language belongs to the so-called literary-historical languages. It is called "dead", like some other languages, because now there is no people who would communicate in it [1, p. 189-197]. But knowledge of the Latin language has always been considered a sign of high culture and education. And today the words of the Roman orator, philosopher and writer Cicero remain relevant: "Non tam praeclare est scire Latine, quam turpe nescire" = It is so commendable to know the Latin language, how shameful not to know it.

There is a rich literary and scientific heritage in Latin. These are the works of Roman poets: Virgil, Horace, Ovid, Catullus; works of famous scientists, philosophers, orators: Cicero, Caesar, Lucretius, Seneca, Pliny the Elder and many others. They played a significant role in the formation of European science, culture and art [2]

From time immemorial, the brilliant aphorisms of Latin authors have come down to us: Una dies gradus est vitae. – One day is a stage of life; Tertium non datur. - There is no third; Suum cuique place. - Everyone likes his own; Si sapis, sis apis. - If you are wise, be a bee; Si vis pacem, para bellum. "If you want peace, prepare for war; Simplex sigillum veri. Simplicity is a sign of truth [3]. We use them in everyday communication, in legal and diplomatic practice, we meet them in fiction and scientific literature. Some of these aphorisms have become the mottos of states, associations, unions, scientists, politicians: Noli nocere! - Do no harm! (motto of physicians and pharmacists); Citius, altius, fortius! - Faster, higher, stronger! (The motto of the Olympic Games); Gens una sumus. - We = a single tribe (the motto of chess players); Similia similibus curantur. – Like cures like (the motto of homeopaths) and others [4, p. 162-166]. Many Latin words relating to different spheres of human activity have become international: consensus, sponsor, conversion, pluralism, student, pharmacist, scholarship, reaction, experiment, faculty, rector, dean, graduate student, auditorium, institute and many others.

The Latin language (Lingua Latina) got its name from the word Latium - the name of a small area in the center of the Apennine Peninsula.

The World Health Organization publishes the International Pharmacopoeia ("Pharmacopoea internationalis") - a list of the main international Latin names of drugs. Recipes are written in Latin in many countries.

The words "pharmacy", "pharmacist", "pharmaceutical" come from the Greek word pharmakon - a medicine, which in turn was borrowed by Greek from the ancient Egyptian language, and was written under the image of the ancient Egyptian god of the art of healing Thoth.

The word "term" is of Latin origin (from terminus - border, edge, boundary. The term is the name of the Roman god of borders). The main purpose of the term is to accurately and unambiguously define and name the scientific concept [11, p. 128-136]. The term can be either one single, independent word (organism, tissues, cell, gene, appendicitis, fluorography, organ, disease, ontogeny, etc.), or a phrase (chest, occipital bone, connection of the bones of the skull, general myology, hypertension, sanitation, radiation hygiene, etc.). The set of terms of a certain area of knowledge is called terminology. It is necessary to distinguish between the actual terms - the names of general concepts, and nomenclature names - names denoting single concepts [12, p. 201 - 206]. The set of nomenclature names within a certain classification system forms the corresponding nomenclature. There are botanical, microbiological Latin international nomenclature. Modern medical and pharmaceutical terminology is the result of centuries of development of theoretical and practical medicine and pharmacy, many special disciplines that study the research, production and use of drugs [13]. They consist of terminological subsystems of a number of areas of knowledge. Mastering the basics of Latin grammar, knowledge of a certain lexical minimum, Greek-Latin word-formation elements and the structure of special terms ensures the professional terminological literacy of the future medical specialist.

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